

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)
Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication
ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060
Publisher: Binas Publishing
Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“TWINKLE, CHASE AND SKYE”

You came into my challenged life,
Gave me hope amidst the strife.
Who knew a twinkle, so cute and bright,
Could ease my heart, bring joy to light?

The world is full of heavy regrets,
Yet your blue eyes and fur like snow sets
Each day aglow with a brand-new hue,
Chasing dreams toward tomorrows anew.

Though skies may be gray, they seem bright as day,
Your little whimpers hasten my dismay.
Please, my dear one, smile just for me;
No regrets linger from what used to be.

My four-legged children, my fur family dear,
Each time I come home, happiness draws near.
Frolicking in and out of my blissful life,
Tomorrow's not promised; today I must strive.

Leave me not, little ones; don't say goodbye.
Happiness blooms with you by my side.
Fur of brown and white with eyes so blue—
Twinkle and Chase and Skye—my heart belongs to you.